

Polarographic Behaviour of the Metal Complexes in Various Aqueous-alkanol Mixtures. Part I. Cadmium-propylenediamine Complexes in Aqueous-methanol Mixtures

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The reduction of Cd(II) in propylenediamine was found to be reversible and diffusion controlled. The complexes of cadmium with propylenediamine in various percentages of methanol have been studied polarographically, using the Lingane's method and DeFord Hume treatment as extended by Irving. Increase in the stability constants and positive shift of the half-wave potential of the metal ion was observed with increase in methanol concentration. The percentage composition of the various complexed and uncomplexed species in 25% methanol is presented.

VARIOUS papers have been published on cadmium complexes with propylenediamine using different methods¹⁻³. Authors have studied Cd(II) complexes with propylenediamine in aqueous media polarographically⁴. The present investigations are devoted to the polarographic behaviour of the complexes formed by cadmium(II) with propylenediamine in various aqueous mixtures of methanol.

Experimental

The polarograms were obtained with a manual set up. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics: $m = 2.12$ mg/sec., $t = 4.6$ sec (in an open circuit). A constant temperature, $30^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$ was maintained by Haake type ultra thermostat. All the half-wave potentials were referred to saturated calomel electrode. Reagent grade chemicals were used. The stock solutions (M/40) of Cd^{2+} was prepared from its nitrate and standardised as usual⁵.

Solutions containing 1.00 mM of Cd(II) and various concentrations of propylenediamine in 25%, 50% and 75% methanol (by volume) were prepared. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 by adding sodium perchlorate. All the solutions were polarographed after deaeration with purified nitrogen gas presaturated with aqueous methanol solution. The electrolysis was carried out in a H type cell saturated with a NaCl agar agar plug.

Results and Discussion

A well defined, diffusion controlled wave for reduction of cadmium-propylene diamine complexes appeared in each case for all the three percentages of methanol. The plots of $\log i/i_a - i$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ were found to be linear having slope of the order of 31 ± 2 mV showed the reversibility of the reduction ($n = 2$). The E_1 values were obtained by these plots.

The plots of E_1 vs $-\log C_X$ were found to be straight lines in all the aqueous methanol systems (25%, 50% and 75%). The value of coordination number ' p ' was obtained by the relation

$$\frac{\Delta E_1}{\Delta \log C_X} = - \frac{p}{n} 0.0601$$

where ΔE_1 = shift in E_1

C_X = ligand concentration

n = number of electrons involved in reaction comes to be 3 in all the systems.

Formation constants ($\log \beta_3$) calculated by Lingane's⁶ method are 11.60, 12.23, and 12.63 in 25%, 50% and 75% methanol respectively

As the complexation occurs in steps, DeFord and Hume⁷ method as modified by Irving⁸ was applied to determine the composition and stability constants of the complexes. The detail of the method has been described earlier⁹. The results has been incorporated in Table 1.2. The $F_j([X])$ vs C_X plots for cadmium-propylenediamine system in 25%, 50% and 75% (Figs. 1-3) showed the presence of two species MX_1 and MX_3 having overall formation constants as follows:

Stability constants	aqueous ⁴	25%	50%	75%
B_1	1×10^9	6×10^8	1×10^9	3×10^9
B_2	1×10^9	—	—	—
B_3	34.5×10^{10}	7.5×10^{11}	12.8×10^{11}	5.1×10^{12}

Although in aqueous media all the three species formed (MX_1 , MX_2 and MX_3) were stable. How-

TABLE 1— $E_{1/2}$ AND i_d VALUES FOR CADMIUM PROPYLENEDIAMINE SYSTEM IN AQUEOUS MIXTURES OF METHANOL

C_x (Moles)	2 % Methanol		50% Methanol		75% Methanol	
	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	i_d (div.)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	i_d (div.)	$E_{1/2}$ (-V vs SCE)	i_d (div.)
0.0	0.569	101.0	0.5560	88.0	0.5460	100.0
0.05	0.810	100.0	0.8000	88.0	0.8075	99.0
0.10	0.830	91.0	0.8270	87.0	0.8350	99.0
0.15	0.8467	92.0	0.8430	83.0	0.8510	98.5
0.20	0.8580	87.0	0.8542	85.0	0.8620	92.0
0.25	0.8670	86.0	0.8635	85.0	0.8710	92.0
0.30	0.8732	84.0	0.8710	85.0	0.8772	94.5
0.35	0.8800	84.0	0.8767	84.0	0.8845	87.0
0.40	0.8860	86.0	0.8815	85.0	0.8890	87.5
0.45	0.8905	82.0	—	—	—	—
0.50	—	—	0.8900	85.0	0.8980	87.0

 Fig 1 Plots of $F_j(C_x)$ vs C_x in 25% methanol

 Fig 2 Plots of $F_j(C_x)$ vs C_x in 50% methanol

 Fig 3 Plots of $F_j(C_x)$ vs C_x for Cd^{++} -propylene-diamine system in 75% methanol

 Fig 4 %Composition of various species in Cd^{++} -propylene-diamine system in 25% methanol

over, in presence of methanol, the second species (MX_2) was unstable; thus only two species were present (MX_1 and MX_3). Analysis of the complexes

with propylenediamine shows that the stability of the complexes increases with increase in the methanol content

The displacement of the half-wave potential of the metals to more positive values as the methanol concentration is increased, is due to the energy of bond between the metal and alcohol being slightly lower than the energy of the bond with water. As a result, the discharge of an ion containing methanol being slightly lower than the energy of the bond with water.

The percentage distribution of cadmium present in various forms as function of logarithm of ligand concentration was calculated by the equations,

$$\frac{M}{C_M} = \frac{1}{F_0([X])} \text{ and } \frac{MX_j}{C_M} = \frac{\beta_j([X])}{F_0([X])}$$

where M denotes the concentration of uncomplexed metal ion, MX_j is concentration of the j th complex species and C_M , the total metal ion added to the system, the results are shown in Fig. 4.

As the reduction of Cd(II) is diffusion controlled, it can be estimated polarographically.

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References

1. H. M. IRVING, R. J. P. WILLIAMS, D. T. FERRETT and A. E. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3494.
2. J. L. HALL and THOMAS J. CARPENTER, *Proc. W. Va. Acad. Sci.*, 1953, 25, 37.
3. Y. SHIGENOBU, I' HARUKO, K. YOSHIO, F. JUNNUSURE and S. KAZUO, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1969, 42, 3148.
4. A. K. MAHESHWARI, D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *Monatshefte Für Chemie* (communicated).
5. A. I. VOGEL, 'Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., London, Edn. 3, 1961, p.
6. J. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 29, 1.
7. DEFORD D. and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5321.
8. H. IRVING, 'Advances in Polarography', Ed. I. S. Langmuir, Pergamon Press, London, 1960, Vol. 1, p. 42.
9. M. M. PALRECHA and J. N. GAUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 313.